

COMPARISON OF POST-OPERATIVE SHOULDER TIP PAIN IN LOW PRESSURE VERSUS STANDARD PRESSURE PNEUMOPERITONEUM DURING LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY

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Abstract

Objective: "To compare the mean post-operative shoulder tip pain in low pressure versus standard pressure pneumoperitoneum during laparoscopic cholecystectomy".

Study design: Randomized controlled trial

Study place and duration: Department of Surgery, Sharif Medical City Hospital, Lahore from 1-7-2024 to 1-1-2025.

Methodology: Sixty patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled from operation theatre and randomly divided in two groups. In group A, patients underwent laparoscopy under low pressure CO₂ i.e. 8-10 mmHg. In group B, patients underwent laparoscopy under standard pressure CO₂ i.e. 12-14 mmHg. After 4, 8, 12 and 24 hours of surgery, patients were examined for shoulder tip pain score. All this data was recorded in proforma and analyzed through SPSS version 26.

Results: In this trial, the mean age of patients was 42.20±13.92 years in low pressure group while 45.77±12.23 years in standard pressure group. In low pressure group, there were 9 (30%) males and 21 (70%) females. While in standard pressure group, there were 5 (16.7%) males and 25 (83.3%) females. After 24 hours of surgery, the median pain score in low pressure group was 1.00 (IQR: 1.00) while in standard pressure group was 2.50 (IQR: 3.0), (p-value <0.0001). In low pressure group, 14 (46.7%) patients had no pain, and 16 (53.3%) had mild (VAS 1-3) pain. In standard pressure group, 17 (56.7%) patients had mild (VAS 1-3) pain, and 13 (43.3%) patients had moderate pain (p-value<0.0001).

Conclusion: Thus, low pressure pneumoperitoneum has better outcome and less

pain as compared to standard pressure pneumoperitoneum after laparoscopic cholecystectomy

INTRODUCTION

Due to its less invasive nature, quicker recovery times, and lower postoperative discomfort, laparoscopic surgery is recommended over laparotomy. Using carbon dioxide (CO₂) gas to induce pneumoperitoneum is the most popular technique for creating a stable laparoscopic surgical field.¹⁻³ Increases in intraperitoneal pressure brought on by the gas are the primary cause of complications commonly linked to CO₂ gas-based laparoscopic surgery. The diaphragm rises toward the lungs when CO₂ gas is injected because the gas raises the pressure in the abdominal cavity.⁴ Hypoventilation and a reduction in total lung capacity are linked to this physiological alteration. In order to maintain balance, CO₂ injected into the abdominal cavity is quickly absorbed into the blood through the peritoneum, which can result in hypercarbia, acidosis, and elevated end-tidal CO₂.^{5, 6}

Abdominal and especially shoulder tip discomfort are the hallmarks of post-laparoscopic pain syndrome, which is widely known and commonly occurs after laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Three categories may be used to categorize the causes of post-laparoscopic pain: shoulder, incision, and visceral. Although the exact etiology of shoulder discomfort is unknown, it is generally believed to be overstretching of the diaphragmatic muscle fibers as a result of a high incidence of insufflations.^{7, 8} The primary cause of this shoulder tip discomfort is CO₂-induced pneumoperitoneum.

Shoulder tip discomfort during laparoscopic cholecystectomy is caused by carbon dioxide insufflation. It is usually believed that a high carbon dioxide pressure causes the diaphragmatic muscle fibers to overstretch, which is the cause of shoulder discomfort.^{8, 9} However, reducing intra-abdominal pressure may potentially lessen the effect of pneumoperitoneum on intra-abdominal organ blood circulation and cardiopulmonary performance. But since there is still insufficient proof, the argument is still open.^{3, 8}

Swathi et al., conducted a study Pre-operative predictors of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy: a comparative study between two scoring systems BMI greater than 27.5 kg/m², a palpable gallbladder, a history of acute cholecystitis hospitalization Both univariate and multivariate logistic regression revealed that the existence of pericholecystic edoema, a wall thickness of more than 4 mm on sonography, and these factors were statistically significant. RSCLO was better in predicting easy cholecystectomy, or little risk for conversion, but NSS was better at predicting severe, extremely difficult cholecystectomies, or "converted cases," with a sensitivity of 100%.¹⁰

The purpose of this study was to compare the post-operative shoulder tip discomfort following laparoscopic cholecystectomy in low pressure and standard pressure pneumoperitoneum. According to published research, following laparoscopic cholecystectomy, low pressure pneumoperitoneum produces better results and causes less discomfort than normal pressure pneumoperitoneum. But limited data has been reported before. Although trials have conducted in local clinics but still low pressure pneumoperitoneum is not in current practice. Therefore, there is a need to conduct a trial and collect evidence for local population in favor of more appraise and successful method for laparoscopic cholecystectomy to reduce post-laparoscopic should tip pain. So that in future we can be able to implement findings of this study in local setting. This will help to improve our practice and knowledge and can modify the outcomes with better treatment protocol and reduce the chances of post-laparoscopic should tip pain.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

"After approval from the ethical review board (ERC letter no SMDC/SMRC 313-23), this Randomized controlled trial was carried out in the Department of Surgery, Sharif Medical City Hospital, Lahore from 1-7-2024 to 1-1-2025. By using openepi.com, sample size of 60 cases; 30 in each group is calculated with

95% confidence level, 90% power of study and mean shoulder tip pain i.e. 0.34 ± 1.0 with low pressure and 2.86 ± 2.64 with standard pressure.¹¹ Patients who fulfilled following criteria were recruited after applying Non-Probability, consecutive sampling technique.

Inclusion: Patients of age 20-70 years, both genders, undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy to remove stones from gall bladder under general anesthesia were enrolled. Cholelithiasis was diagnosed on ultrasonography in a patient with history of right hypochondrium pain.

Exclusion: Patients with traumatic wounds, recurrent disease, ischemic heart diseases and need to convert to open cholecystectomy, pregnancy, Hb<10 g/dl, alcoholic were excluded.

Patients were enrolled from operation theatre and before induction of anesthesia, informed consent was taken. Demographics including name, age,

gender, BMI, duration of cholelithiasis, stone size, medical and general history including hypertension, dyslipidemia, diabetes, smoking and life style, were noted. Then patients were randomly divided in two groups by using lottery method. In group A, patients underwent laparoscopy under low pressure CO₂ i.e. 8-10 mmHg. In group B, patients underwent laparoscopy under standard pressure CO₂ i.e. 12-14 mmHg. Then surgery was performed as per standard criteria and operative time was noted. All patients were shifted in post-surgical wards and were followed-up there for 24 hours. After 24 hours, patients were examined for shoulder tip pain score. Pain was assessed on visual analogue scale score. VAS 0-10 was used, where 0= no pain, 1-3 is mild pain, 4-7 is moderate pain and 8-10 is severe pain. All this data was recorded in proforma.

Figure-1: Patient Flow Diagram (n= 60)

All the data was entered and analyzed through SPSS version 26. “Shapiro-Wilk test was applied to determine the normality of data. Both groups were compared for mean shoulder tip pain by using independent samples t-test. P-value ≤ 0.05 was taken as significant.”

RESULTS

In this trial, the mean age of patients was 42.20 ± 13.92 years in low pressure group while 45.77 ± 12.23 years in standard pressure group. In low

pressure group, there were 9 (30%) male patients and 21 (70%) female patients. While in standard pressure group, there were 5 (16.7%) male patients and 25 (83.3%) female patients. The mean BMI of patients was 39.83 ± 8.00 vs. 33.43 ± 10.59 in low and standard pressure group, respectively. In low pressure group, there were 5 (16.7%) smokers while in standard pressure group, 4 (13.3%) were smokers. In low pressure group, 23 (76.7%) patients had sedentary lifestyle while in standard pressure group, 29 (96.7%) patients had sedentary lifestyle. In low pressure group, 14 (46.7%) were diabetic, 10 (33.3%)

were hypertensive and 15 (50%) had hyperlipidemia. In standard pressure group, 24 (80%) were diabetic, 17 (56.7%) were hypertensive and 18 (60%) had hyperlipidemia. The mean duration of cholelithiasis was 15.73±5.42 vs. 12.90±6.50 in low and standard pressure group, respectively, the mean stone size was 3.52±1.50 vs. 3.02±1.48 and mean operative time was 42.43±9.05 vs. 42.13±9.29, respectively (p-value>0.05). Table I

“Shapiro-Wilk test” was applied to check the normality of data and it has been observed that the tests results were highlight significant depicting that data was not following normal distribution, then non-parametric test was applied to check the significant difference of pain score in both groups. Table II

Box plot depicting distribution of pain score in both trial groups. Fig I

After 24 hours of surgery, the median pain score in low pressure group was 1.00 (IQR: 1.00) while in standard pressure group was 2.50 (IQR: 3.0). The difference was calculated to be highlight significant (p-value <0.0001). In low pressure group, 14 (46.7%) patients had no pain, 16 (53.3%) had mild (VAS 1-3) pain, while no patient complaint of moderate or severe pain. In standard pressure group, 17 (56.7%) patients had mild (VAS 1-3) pain, and 13 (43.3%) patients had moderate pain, but no patient complaint of severe pain. The difference was found to be significant and pain after low pressure surgery had better outcomes than standard pressure group (p-value<0.0001). Table III”

Table I: Basic profile of patients with cholelithiasis (n = 60)

	Trial group		p-value
	Low pressure	Standard pressure	
n	30	30	
Age (in years)	42.20±13.92	45.77±12.23	0.296
Gender			
Male	9 (30%)	5 (16.7%)	0.222
Female	21 (70%)	25 (83.3%)	
BMI (kg/m2)	39.83±8.00	33.43±10.59	0.011
Smoking	5 (16.7%)	4 (13.3%)	0.718
Lifestyle			
Sedentary	23 (76.7%)	29 (96.7%)	0.023
Active	7 (23.3%)	1 (3.3%)	
Medical history			
Diabetes	14 (46.7%)	24 (80%)	0.007
Hypertension	10 (33.3%)	17 (56.7%)	0.069
Hyperlipidemia	15 (50%)	18 (60%)	0.436
Duration of Cholelithiasis	15.73±5.42	12.90±6.50	0.072
Size of stone	3.52±1.50	3.02±1.48	0.201
Operative time	42.43±9.05	42.13±9.29	0.900

Table II: Shapiro-Wilk test to determine the normality of data

	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.
Shoulder tip pain	.855	60	.000

Fig I: Shoulder tip pain

Table III: Postoperative findings of the trial (n = 60)

	Trial group		P-value
	Low pressure	Standard pressure	
n	30	30	
Shoulder tip pain	1.00 (IQR: 1.00)	2.50 (IQR: 3.0)	0.000*
Pain			
Absent / none	14 (46.7%)	0 (0%)	0.000
Mild	16 (53.3%)	17 (56.7%)	
Moderate	0 (0%)	13 (43.3%)	
Severe	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	

* = Mann-Whitney U test was applied to compare median pain score in both trial groups

DISCUSSION

In this trial, we observed that after 24 hours of surgery, the median pain score in low pressure group was 1.00 (IQR: 1.00) while in standard pressure group was 2.50 (IQR: 3.0), (p-value <0.0001). In low pressure group, 14 (46.7%) patients had no pain, and 16 (53.3%) had mild (VAS 1-3) pain. In standard pressure group, 17 (56.7%) patients had mild (VAS 1-3) pain, and 13 (43.3%) patients had moderate pain (p-value<0.0001).

Thapa et al., found that the mean shoulder tip pain was 0.22±0.41 with low pressure while 0.40±0.70 with standard pressure after 4 hours of surgery. But after 8, 12 and 24 hours, the pain score was significantly less with low pressure (0.34±1.0) than standard pressure (2.86±2.64) after laparoscopic cholecystectomy.¹¹ Sattar et al., conducted a similar

trial and reported that the mean pain score with standard pressure was 3.46±0.74 and with low pressure was 2.84±0.75 (p-value <0.05).¹² Anwaar et al., also conducted a similar study and concluded that with standard pressure, Shoulder tip discomfort was experienced by 36% of patients and by 8% of patients under low pressure (p-value < 0.001). In terms of the incidence of post-operative shoulder tip discomfort, they found that low pressure laparoscopic cholecystectomy is superior to normal pressure cholecystectomy.¹³

In order to do laparoscopic surgeries, the pneumoperitoneum must be created. In order to do this, surgeons have historically injected carbon dioxide gas into the peritoneal cavity during port placement, creating a pneumoperitoneum of up to 14–15 mmHg. ¹⁴ In a different research, Gurusamy

and Samraj reviewed a number of clinical studies assessing the effects of standard and low pressures on post-operative shoulder tip discomfort and post-operative healing. According to their examination of the Cochrane database, the low pressure groups saw a decreased incidence of shoulder tip discomfort. [15](#) Diaphragmatic stretching, chemical irritation of the peritoneum by carbonic acids from carbon dioxide, and sympathetic nervous system activation resulting from hypercarbia, which amplifies the local tissue inflammatory response and causes splanchnic mucosal ischemia, could be the precise mechanism of pain associated with pneumoperitoneum following laparoscopy. [16](#), [17](#) Diaphragmatic distention that irritates the phrenic nerve distribution region may be the source of right shoulder discomfort in high pressure pneumoperitoneum. The incidence and intensity of referred shoulder discomfort were decreased by removing the residual exogenous carbon dioxide at the conclusion of the procedure. [16](#), [18](#)

Nasajiyan et al 12% of patients having laparoscopic cholecystectomy experienced post-operative discomfort in the low pressure group, compared to 36% in the normal pressure group, according to a research. [19](#) Postoperative discomfort is considerably reduced when low-pressure pneumoperitoneum (8 mm Hg) is used for laparoscopic cholecystectomy. However, the surgeon's comfort may be at risk while using this low-pressure pneumoperitoneum. [20](#)

Abdallah et al., also found through a randomized trial that the mean postoperative shoulder tip pain was 3 with low pressure surgery while 13 with standard pressure surgery ($P < 0.005$). [21](#) The average level of discomfort in the group undergoing low pressure surgery was 0.28 ± 0.90 , whereas the group undergoing normal pressure surgery had 1.31 ± 2.38 ($p = 0.001$), according to a research by Ali et al. The low pressure surgery group's average operating time was 27.84 ± 6.078 minutes, whereas the standard pressure surgery group's was 28.51 ± 7.45 minutes. [22](#) In a 2019 research, Meena et al. discovered that the mean pain score after four hours under low pressure was 6.2 ± 0.82 , while the mean score at standard pressure was 6.8 ± 0.98 ($p \text{ value} < 0.001$). [23](#) This is also in line with Kandil et al.'s findings, which demonstrated that shoulder tip discomfort began to manifest 4-6 hours after surgery, progressively

worsened until around 12 hours later, and then began to subside. [24](#)

CONCLUSION

Thus, low pressure pneumoperitoneum has better outcome and less pain as compared to standard pressure pneumoperitoneum after laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Now, we have found that low pressure pneumoperitoneum can lead to better and successful method for laparoscopic cholecystectomy to reduce post-laparoscopic should tip pain. Now, we will implement these findings in local setting.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

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